

A primary human hepatocyte culture model of HBV infection.

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We defined the cellular transcriptome during HBV infection using a primary human hepatocyte culture model and RNA-sequencing. We demonstrate here silencing of *Cxcl1* and *Ccl2* in HBV infection. cells activated transporter *Abcg8* and short chain fatty acid metabolism factor *Acs11*. A family of Cyp enzymes was induced including *Cyp2c1*, *Cyp2c8*, *Cyp4f3* and *Cyp2c9*. Lineage factor *Mitf* was silenced indicating identity changes induced by infection. Cells infected with HBV activated *Slc6a1*, *Slco2b1*, and *Slc22a7*.

Citations

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